

Status and Development Prospects of Livestock in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article provides information on the general state of livestock farming in our Republic, changes in the number of livestock.

Keywords: Livestock farming, cattle breeding, milk, meat, growth, development, livestock products.

Introduction.

As a result of the adoption of a number of decisions and important measures taken to develop the livestock sector in Uzbekistan, its consistent growth is ensured. Cattle breeding is the leading branch of animal husbandry in our republic and plays a major role in satisfying the population's demand for meat and dairy products.

In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-120 dated February 8, 2022 “On measures to further develop livestock farming and strengthen the livestock feed base”, in 2022-2023, in cooperation with the State Committee for the Development of Veterinary Medicine and Livestock, at least 1 enterprise producing and processing meat and dairy products in each district will organize the supply of livestock to households in a cooperative manner and the processing and sale of the produced products; in districts with a shortage of irrigated land for the cultivation of the feed base, opportunities are being created to establish the production and processing of meat and dairy products in a cooperative manner in order to fully satisfy consumer demand for meat and dairy products. According to the results of 2022, the share of livestock farming in the total volume of agricultural production reached 48.2%. In accordance with the resolution, this dissertation work serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks set, which are aimed at increasing the production of milk and beef, improving cattle breeds, and increasing crop yields.

Research and methods. The data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2025 were analyzed using zootechnical and analytical methods. The data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2025 were analyzed using zootechnical and analytical methods to determine the number of livestock in all categories of farms, the number of livestock products produced and grown, and the regions that led in the production of these products.

Result and discussion.

As of January 1, 2024, the following livestock breeding entities exist in the Republic of Uzbekistan. There are a total of 7919 livestock farms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which were analyzed by region.

If we analyze the livestock farms by region, the first place is taken by Kashkadarya region, which accounts for 1263 of the total farms in the Republic, or 15.9 percent. The second place is taken by Samarkand region, which accounts for 855 of the total farms, or 10.8 percent, and the third place is taken by the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which accounts for 769 of the total farms, or 9.7 percent. So,

these 3 regions account for 2887 of the total livestock farms in the Republic, or 36.4 percent. In terms of cattle breeding, the following regions of the Republic are in proportional terms: Tashkent, Jizzakh, Syrdarya, Khorezm, Andijan, Fergana, Bukhara, Surkhandarya, Namangan and Navoi regions, with the following total cattle breeding farms: 751 or 9.5 percent; 730 or 9.2 percent; 706 or 8.9 percent; 625 or 7.9 percent; 537 or 6.8 percent; 509 or 6.4 percent; 398 or 5.1 percent; 342 or 4.3 percent; 309 or 3.9 percent and 125 or 1.6 percent.

Analysis of data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic shows that the total number of cattle in all categories of farms in our Republic as of January 1, 2025 was 14,389.8 thousand heads.

When this indicator was analyzed by farms of various forms of ownership, it was observed that of the total 14,389.8 heads of cattle: 1,081.5 thousand heads or 7.5 percent were bred in farms, 13,006.3 thousand heads or 90.4 percent were bred in personal subsidiary farms of farmers and residents, and 302.0 thousand heads or 2.1 percent were bred in farms carrying out agricultural activities.

Of the total number of cattle bred, 5,130.5 thousand heads or 35.6 percent were cows. When analyzing this indicator by farm, it was observed that a total of 5130.5 head of cows are being bred, of which 436.7 thousand heads or 8.5 percent are being bred in farms, 4581.1 thousand heads or 89.3 percent are being bred in private subsidiary farms of farmers and the population, and 112.7 thousand heads or 2.2 percent are being bred in farms carrying out agricultural activities. If we analyze the number of cattle being bred by region, the first place is taken by Samarkand region, where 1765.8 thousand heads or 12.3 percent of the total cattle in the Republic are being bred. The second place is taken by Kashkadarya region, where 1762.7 thousand heads or 12.2 percent of the total cattle in the Republic are being bred, and the third place is taken by Bukhara region, where 1391.6 thousand heads or 9.7 percent of the total cattle in the Republic are being bred. This means that 4,920.1 thousand heads or 34.2 percent of the total cattle breeding in the Republic are bred in these 3 regions.

In terms of the number of cattle, the following regions of the Republic are proportionally ranked: the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan, Fergana, Surkhandarya, Tashkent, Jizzakh, Khorezm, Namangan, Navoi and Syrdarya regions, and the total number of cattle is being bred accordingly: 1260.2 thousand heads or 8.7 percent, 1177.4 thousand heads or 8.2 percent, 1099.7 thousand heads or 7.65 percent, 1090.2 thousand heads or 7.6 percent, 1019.9 thousand heads or 7.1 percent, 982.1 thousand heads or 6.8 percent, 975.6 thousand heads or 6.8 percent, 795.6 thousand heads or 5.5 percent, 554.5 thousand heads or 3.85 percent, 514.5 thousand heads or 3.6 percent.

Table 1. Information on the number of cattle in the Republic of Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2024, thousand heads

Provinces	Cattle		From here the cows	
	Total	%	Total	%
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1260,2	102,3	351,1	101,4
Andijan	1177,4	101,9	408,9	102,5
Bukhara	1391,6	102,0	456,8	102,3
Jizzakh	982,1	101,8	275,3	101,4
Kashkadarya	1762,7	102,0	583,2	102,1
Navoi	554,5	101,6	226,4	102,2
Namangan	795,6	102,0	268,6	101,4
Samarkand	1765,8	101,8	756,0	100,8
Surkhandarya	1090,2	102,1	402,0	101,9
Syrdarya	514,5	101,5	186,2	102,7
Tashkent	1019,9	101,3	431,9	100,9
Fergana	1099,7	101,1	404,7	102,4
Khorezm	975,6	100,8	369,4	100,9
Total	14389,8	101,8	5130,5	101,7

When we analyzed the number of cattle bred in the regions by farms of different forms of ownership, we obtained the following data: 1172.4 heads or 93.0 percent, 1083.0 thousand heads or 92.0 percent, 1235.8 thousand heads or 88.8 percent, 874.5 thousand heads or 89.0 percent, 1591.0 thousand heads or 90.3 percent, 487.1 thousand heads 87.8 percent, 730.7 thousand heads or 91.8 percent, 1641.4 thousand heads or 93.0 percent, 996.8 thousand heads or 91.4 percent, 442.1 thousand heads 85.9 percent, 871.6 thousand heads or 85.5 percent, 1002.3 thousand heads or 91.1 percent, 877.6 thousand heads or 90.0 percent are bred in private subsidiary farms of farmers and residents. The remaining 6.9; 8.0; 11.2; 11.0; 9.8; 12.2; 8.2; 7.0; 8.5; 14.1; 14.5; 8.8 and 10.1 percent are owned by farms and organizations carrying out agricultural activities, respectively.

As of January 1, 2025, information on livestock products produced in all categories of farms of the republic is presented in Table 2.

As of January 1, 2025, the total amount of beef and poultry meat produced amounted to 2,942,494 tons, an increase of 3.9 percent compared to the previous year. Of the total meat produced, 188,060 tons, or 6.4 percent, were produced on farms, 2,488,601 tons, or 84.6 percent, on private subsidiary farms of farmers and the population, and 265,833 tons, or 9.0 percent, were produced in organizations engaged in agricultural activities. As of January 1, 2025, a total of 12,443,841 tons of milk were produced. The growth rate compared to the previous year is 4.0 percent. Of the total milk produced, 740,598 tons, or 6.0 percent, were produced on farms, 11,512,364 tons, or 92.5 percent, on private subsidiary farms of farmers and the population, and 190,879 tons, or 1.5 percent, were produced in organizations engaged in agricultural activities.

Table 2. Production of meat and dairy products in the Republic of Uzbekistan (January 1, 2025)

№	Indicators	Product production, tons	
		Beef and poultry (live weight)	Milk
1	In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a total of	2 942 494	12 443 841
2	Including: Farms	188 060	740 598
3	Dehkan (personal assistant) farms	2 488 601	11 512 364
4	Organizations engaged in agricultural activities	265 833	190 879

Conclusion.

In our republic, compared to the previous year, cattle increased by 1.8 percent, of which cows by 1.7 percent, while this indicator was observed in farmers, dehkans and personal subsidiary farms and organizations engaged in agricultural activities, cattle increased by 3.4; 1.6; 0.9; of which cows by 3.1; 1.5; 2.7 percent.

In the production of products from the cattle breeding sector produced in our republic, compared to the previous year, total meat produced increased by 3.9 percent, total milk produced by 4.0 percent. This indicator was observed in farmers, dehkans and personal subsidiary farms, total meat produced by 9.6; 4.1; and in organizations engaged in agricultural activities, a decrease of 2.2 percent was observed; total milk produced by 4.6; 3.8; increased by 12.0 percent.

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